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Review Paper

Blood Grouping and Typing Methods: Current Insights and Recent Advancements

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ABSTRACT

Blood grouping is a vital process in transfusion medicine. Usually, blood grouping is performed using serological techniques based on antigen–antibody interactions such as test tube method that is the gold standard method for grouping of blood. Blood grouping reagents are crucial instruments in immunohematology, for identifying blood group antigens on red blood cells, such as Rh and ABO. In this review, we have outlined various blood grouping systems and several techniques for blood grouping including test tubes, gel cards, rapid cards, and more recent technologies like molecular imprinting, ultrasound backscattering along with blood group genotyping, molecular typing of blood cells based on SNV and real-time PCR are discussed. The role of current computational techniques in blood group prediction methods for blood group determination is also included in the review. With the advances in bioinformatics, many new processes have been developed that predicts blood group antigens directly from genetic sequences through (computational) methods that are based on genome sequencing, and structural bioinformatics, thereby providing high-throughput, accurate, and cost-effective alternatives to traditional tube testing methods

INTRODUCTION

A blood group antigen is defined as polymorphism on RBCs (platelets and neutrophils) that differ between individuals and stimulates production of an immune antibody following exposure via pregnancy or blood transfusion.¹ Blood grouping reagents are used to type the blood cells of an individual on the basis of antigen present on the

surface of RBC. Blood group typing is the process of testing RBCs to determine and confirm the type of antigens present on the surface of the red blood cells.² The analysis of Red Blood Cells in order to identify the nature of antigens on the surface of the red cells is called Blood Group typing. There occurs an immuno- chemical reaction of specific antisera and the antigens present on the cells

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surface that causes haemagglutination reaction or blood clumping.

Though, approximately three hundred genetically-different blood groups have been identified, still, the ABO and Rh blood grouping system plays predominant role in transfusion services. Incompatibility in transfusion could lead to serious adverse reaction in patients. Hence cross-matching testing is highly recommended for the donor blood and the patient sample, before the transfusion.³ Adverse transfusion reaction has been an extensive area of research since long. Mild symptoms may include Localized cutaneous reactions, Urticaria, rash Pruritus (itching), whereas the Moderately severe symptoms may be Flushing, Urticaria, Rigors, Fever, Restlessness, Tachycardia, Anxiety, pruritus (itching), Palpitations, Mild dyspnoea and Headache. However, Life threatening situation arises may be Rigors, Fever, Restlessness, Hypotension, Tachycardia, Haemoglobinuria (red urine), Unexplained bleeding (DIC), Anxiety, Chest pain, Pain near infusion site, Respiratory distress, loin/back pain, Headache, Dyspnoea.⁴ The more or less severe complications include overburdening of the recipient's circulatory system by excessive, too hasty transfusion or the transfer of diseases from donor to recipient.⁵

The market for blood group typing was estimated to be worth USD 2.31 billion in 2025 and is expected to increase at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 9.60% from USD 2.52 billion in 2026 to USD 5.27 billion by 2034. With a 34.70% market share in 2025, North America led the world market for blood group typing.⁶

Collection and further processing of the donor sample is of absolute importance, as improper product handling after collection may lead to few of the non-immunologic reactions, that can occur due to the physical effects of blood components or infection spread of certain disease as reported in case of septic transfusion reactions due to bacterial

contamination that is usually caused by bacterial/endotoxin contamination of a blood product. Sometimes transfusion-associated volume overload (TACO) and hypothermia happen that is dependent on various blood factors that may be inherently present in the blood.⁷ This review highlights various blood grouping systems and the current methods to characterize them including test tubes, gel card, rapid cards methods and advanced techniques like Molecular imprinting, ultrasound backscattering along with Blood Group genotyping, Molecular Typing of Blood cells based on SNV and real time PCR. The review also discusses the role of modern computational methods in blood group prediction approaches for blood group determination. These cutting-edge methods have established themselves to be among the most intriguing tools for current transfusion medicine.

Blood Grouping Systems

ABO Blood Group system

Though ABO/Rh blood grouping system remains to be the most commonly known blood grouping system. The International Society of Blood Transfusion (ISBT) Working Party for Red Cell Immunogenetics and Blood Group Terminology (ISBT WP) states that there are currently 48 recognized blood group systems containing 398 red cell antigens.⁸

ABO system plays an important role in case transfusion and transplantation since humans have clinically significant anti-A and/or anti-B antibodies in their serum above the age 6 months. Blood group A contains antibody against blood group B in serum and vice-versa, while blood group O contains no A/B antigen but both their antibodies in serum.⁹

The blood group antigens specificity is evaluated on the basis of oligosaccharide epitopes (like ABO Antigens) or by their amino acid sequences (like

Kidd, Kell, and Duffy antigens). Many blood group antigens are important for the red cell membrane, but some (like Lewis system) are plasma antigens that are adsorbed on to the red cell surface. The nomenclature of the red blood cells follows the specifications as per the International Society of Blood Transfusion (ISBT) Working Party that was established in 1980 in order to develop terminology according to the blood group genetics.¹⁰ Few of the common blood grouping systems have been listed in the Table 1

The gene determining human ABO blood group is on chromosome 9 and is known as ABO glycosyltransferase. This locus has three main alleles: A, B, and O. All of them is responsible for the production of the glycoprotein. The allelic combination acquired from parents decides the type of glycoproteins found on persons' blood cells determining their ABO blood type.¹¹

The most polymorphic of the human blood groups is The Rh blood group system which is the clinically very significant, next to ABO in transfusion medicine. This group consists of at least 45 independent antigens. The common Rh antigens: D, C or c, and E or e, were originally expressed in order (CDE) but later, the order was changed to DCE. The letter "d" is used to indicate the D-negative phenotype.¹²

Typing for the ABO and D antigens and the antibody screen are also performed for prenatal patients. If an antibody is identified, its potential to cause fetal hemolysis is assessed based on two factors: its ability to cross the placenta, and expression of the corresponding antigen on fetal red cells. Maternal anti-D can cause fetal hemolysis because it is of the IgG class and can cross the placenta, and because the D antigen is well developed on the red cells of a D-positive fetus. On the other hand, Lewis antibodies, which are common in pregnant women, have no adverse effect on the fetus, as they are typically of the IgM class and do not cross the placenta, and because

Lewis antigens are poorly developed on fetal red cells. If an antibody capable of causing fetal hemolysis is present, close monitoring of the pregnancy is indicated.

Blood group antigens are defined by polymorphisms (variant forms prevalent in more than 1% of the population) and other variations that are usually due to single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), nucleotide insertion or deletion, and gene rearrangements.

The ABO antigens are composed of carbohydrate antigens and have terminal sugars on glycolipids and glycoproteins. The H antigen is the precursor of both the A and B antigens. ABO antigens present on red cells are formed on type 2 precursor chains, whereas antigens present in the plasma are formed on type 1 chains. A transferase on the H protein provides N-acetyl galactosamine to the H antigen, generates the A antigen. B transferase on the H protein provides galactose to the H antigen, generates the B antigen. A and B transferases together form both A and B antigens (referred as group AB). If no transferase is present, the H antigen remains unmodified (referred as group O). ABO antigens are found in the fetus at around 5–6 weeks of gestation but are not expressed until 2–4 years of age due to increased branching of the precursor chains with growing. ABO antibodies present in the new borns are maternal acquired antibodies that cross the placenta and come into the fetal circulation. The infant's antibodies develop after 3–6 months of age upto a year. Fully adult antibody levels are met after 5–10 years of age. Differences arising in the levels of ABO antibodies are dependent upon the formation of A or B antigens in the individual. Around 80% of people having blood group A are subgroup A1 and the remaining 20% are Subgroup A2 or other weaker A subgroups. Group B subgroups are relatively rare.

ABO antibodies are naturally occurring and are IgM type, they have the capacity to cause acute

intravascular transfusion reactions, upon transfusion of an incompatible blood component, or acute transplant rejection may occur, if an incompatible organ is transplanted into the patient. IgG class of ABO antibodies are usually present in

group O individuals, and in a pregnant woman, it can cross the placenta. The ABO antigens present on the fetal red cells are not fully expressed, and if at all fetal hemolysis occurs, is usually mild.¹⁰

Table1- Few blood group systems 13

S.No.	Blood group system name	Major antigens
1.	ABO	A, B, A1B, A1
2.	MNS	M, N, S, s, U
3.	P	P ₁
4.	Rh	D, C, E, c, e
5.	Lutheran	Lu ^a , Lu ^b
6.	Kell	K, k, Kp ^a , Kp ^b , Js ^a , Js ^b
7.	Lewis	Le ^a , Le ^b
8.	Duffy	Fy ^a , Fy ^b ,
9.	Kidd	Jk ^a , Jk ^b , Jk ³
10.	Diego	Di ^a , Di ^b , Wr ^a , Wr ^b
11.	Yt	Yt ^a , Yt ^b
12.	Xg	Xga X
13.	Scianna	Sc ¹ , Sc ²
14.	Dombrock	Do ^a , Do ^b , Gy ^a , Hy, Jo ^a
15.	Colton	Co ^a , Co ^b , Co ³
16.	Landsteiner-Weiner	LW
17.	Chido/Rodgers	CH/RG
18.	Gerbich	Ge ² , Ge ³ , Ge ⁴
19.	Cromer	Cr ^a
20.	Knops	Kn ^a , Kn ^b
21.	Indian	In ^a , In ^b
22.	Ok	Ok ^a
23.	Ralph	MER ²
24.	John Milton Hagan	JMH

H-antigen

The precursor of ABO blood group antigens is known as H-antigen. The Hh blood group contains one antigen, the H antigen, which is found on all RBCs and is the building block for the antigens of the ABO blood group. The deficiency of H antigen is called the "Bombay phenotype" (h/h, or Oh) and its prevalence is 1 in 10,000 individuals in India and 1 in a million people in Europe. If blood

transfusion for such people is required, they can receive blood only from other donors who are also H deficient. (A transfusion of "normal" group O blood can trigger a severe transfusion reaction. Persons with the rare Bombay phenotype are homozygous for the H gene (HH), do not express H-antigen on their RBCs. As H-antigen acts as precursor, its absence means the absence of antigen A and B.¹³

Rhesus system

The Rh blood group system is the most polymorphic of the human blood groups, consisting of at least 45 independent antigens and, next to ABO, is the most clinically significant in transfusion medicine, out of which only five are important D,E,e,C,c. A person can either be Rh-positive (D-antigen present) or Rh-negative (D-antigen absent) where anti-Rh antibodies are, normally, not present in the blood of individuals with D-negative RBCs, unless the circulatory system of these individuals has been exposed to D-positive RBCs.¹⁴ The Pregnancies having risk of HDN (Hemolytic Disease of Newborn) are those in which an Rh D-negative mother becomes pregnant with an RhD-positive child (Here, the fetus gets the D antigen from the father). The mother's immune system forms antibodies to the fetal D antigen (anti-D) that are usually of the IgG types that gets transported across the placenta and comes to the fetal circulation. Prophylaxis shots are hence given against Rh immunization with anti-D Immunoglobulins for Rh-negative pregnant women bearing Rh-positive fetus.

MNS antigen system

The antigens of this blood group are present on the sugar-bearing proteins. Two genes encode the MNS antigens: Glycophorin A and Glycophorin B. These are usually IgM types and rarely, associated with transfusion reactions. These lie in the red blood cell (RBC) membrane. Glycophorins are transmembrane, single-pass glycoproteins that contain carbohydrate, mostly in the form of sialic acid. Glycophorins A and B carry the MNS antigens, and they may also serve as receptors for cytokines and pathogens.¹⁵

Lutheran system

Lutheran system has mainly four pairs of allelic antigens expressing single amino acid substitution in the Lutheran glycoprotein that is present in Chromosome 19. Antibodies against this blood group are clinically insignificant.¹⁶

Kell system

Besides ABO and Rh systems, the antigen of Kell system is the third most significant as Anti-K antibody causes severe hemolytic disease of the fetus and newborn (HDFN) and haemolytic transfusion reactions. It was named after a pregnant lady called Kellacher, where it was found in her serum. She showed reactions to the Blood cells of her infant flowed by the hemolytic reactions. A total of 25 Kell antigens have been studied so far.¹⁷

Duffy system

Duffy-antigen is named after a patient named Duffy who was suffering from haemophilia. The antigen is represented as Fy^a and Fy^b. These are allelic pair of glycoproteins that is present in the surface of RBCs. It is a nonspecific receptor for various chemokines and also acts as a receptor for malarial parasite of humans, *Plasmodium vivax*. The antibodies are IgG subtypes and can cause HTR.¹⁸

Kidd system (known as Jk antigen)

Kidd antigen, glycoprotein is present on the membrane of RBCs Kidd antibodies are rare but can cause severe transfusion reactions. These antigens are defined by reactions to an antibody represented as anti-Jk^a. These were discovered in the serum of a pregnant patient named Kidd who delivered a baby with HDFN. Jk^a, Jk^b and Jk³ are found in the Kidd blood group system¹⁹

CURRENT METHODS OF GROUPING RED BLOOD CELLS

The basis of ABO blood grouping lies in the understanding of blood grouping antigen and antibodies where the kind of antigen present on the surface of RBC plays a vital role for the methods of testing to determine the groups of several blood type.

Karl Landsteiner, also known as the father of blood grouping, was awarded the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine in 1930. He demonstrated that the blood from different source upon mixing, forms a clot and blocks the vessels and hence have lethal effect. As the 'Landsteiner's law states: - the plasma contains natural antibodies to A or B, if these antigens are absent from the red cells of that person²⁰. The same has been illustrated in Table 2:

Table-2 Presence of type of antigen and antisera in various blood type determines the blood group

Blood Group	A Blood Group	B Blood Group	AB Blood Group	O Blood Group
Antigen on the surface of Red blood cells	A Antigens	B Antigens	A and B Antigens	No antigens
Antibodies in the plasma	Anti-B Antibody	Anti-B Antibody	No Antibody	Anti-A and Anti-B Antibody

There are several standardized procedures for the routine clinical analysis for blood grouping and typing. Most of the classical methods are qualitative and less sensitive, yet they are widely used in blood banks, clinical laboratories and hospitals due to their simple procedures and inexpensive reagents and equipment requirements. However, in recent times there have been recent reports of molecular blood typing methods owing to certain limitations of the classical methods used. Various classical methods that have been in use are explained further.

Slide Method

The slide method is one of the oldest methods used in blood banks and hospitals for blood group typing. It is performed on a glass slide or on a tile in which a drop of the antisera (Anti-A, Anti-B or Anti-D) is gently added to a drop of patient blood to check if there is any haemagglutination. In such methods, usually the whole blood is used for the estimation. The reaction that is observed with the different reagents used in the test determines the ABO and RhD type of the blood sample under test.

The slide method is very simple and does not require equipment. Though nowadays, it is believed to be less sensitive technique as it only detects interaction between antigens and antibodies (IgM antibody types), hence it is not able to detect incomplete (IgG) antibodies in the patient's blood sample. This technique is most popular in the blood donation camps for preliminary detection of blood groups.²¹

Test Tube Method

One of the most popular methods, also called the "Gold Standard Method" as it is a more sensitive method than the slide method and avoids any false positive result as may be the case in the slide method. The tube method involves testing 2-5% red blood cells under testing and adding equal volumes of the suitable reagent. The result is then observed for the type of agglutination/Grade obtained after centrifugation of the tubes for 1 min at 100 RPM. Both forward and reverse grouping makes the tube method as more reliable method as compared to the slide method. For forward grouping we use a known source of antibodies

(Anti-A, Anti-B/Anti-D or others) to detect the antigens on the red blood cells; however, for Reverse grouping we use the reagent cells with known ABO antigens (previously tested) and

testing the patient's serum for ABO group antibodies.²²

The interpretation of ABO typing through forward and reverse grouping is given in the Table 3:

Table-3 Interpretation of results after forward and reverse grouping

Cell / Forward grouping			Serum/Reverse grouping (with Known cells)			RESULT (Blood Group)
Anti-A	Anti-B	Anti-AB	A _{cell}	B _{cell}	O _{cell}	
+	Neg	+	Neg	+	Neg	A
Neg	+	+	+	Neg	Neg	B
Neg	Neg	Neg	+	+	Neg	O
+	+	+	Neg	Neg	Neg	AB
Neg	Neg	Neg	+	+	+	Bombay Group or any other irregular antibody

The agglutination obtained after centrifugation is graded as 1+ to 4+ reaction as shown the Fig 1:

Fig.1- Figure showing various grades of the reaction in a tube test

Gel Card Method

The gel technique for determination of blood group is based on the principle described by Yves Lapiere on the red blood cell agglutination reactions. A typical gel card is composed of 6-8 microtubes/wells, each having gel suspended in isotonic buffer containing specific antisera, Eg. Anti-A, Anti-B, Anti AB, Anti-D or any other antisera. When red blood cell suspension is added through the opening at the top of each well, the agglutination occurs if the red blood cell antigens react with the corresponding antisera, present in

the gel suspension or in the serum or plasma sample (in the case of reverse grouping test). The gel column acts as a strainer that blocks the agglutinated red blood cells on the top of the well of the gel cards upon centrifugation of the entire gel card. However, all the negative cells that have not agglutinated with the antisera pass through the gel column upon centrifugation of the card. The agglutinated red blood cells get captured at the top of the well whereas the non-agglutinated red blood cells settle down at the bottom of the well forming a pellet.²³

Microtitre Plate Method

In this method, Grouping is carried out in micro wells as it is quick, very simple, cost-effective and easy to read, infer and verify the hemagglutination reactions. These are composed of rigid polystyrene microtiter plates containing 96 U or v shaped bottom wells and the plates are covered to prevent evaporation and are incubated 10 - 30 min at room temperature. After centrifugation 30 - 60 sec at 100xg, using a centrifuge adapter for plates, the plates are agitated by a shaker for 10 - 30 sec, to resuspend the cells completely. The agglutination reactions are read from the bottom of the plate by a reading device with an illuminated and magnifying mirror. The advantages of the microtiter hemagglutination method is clearly evident by rapid detection. This method is sensitive and ideal for large number of samples.²⁴

Rapid Blood Grouping Cards

These are type of rapid detection device in which the absorbant paper strip is impregnated with a matrix of antibodies and dye. When a drop of blood is applied, lines of colour develop as the blood spreads across the strip and reacts with the antibodies. Such type of test is based on the principle of lateral flow guided by capillary action. Reagents are pre-dried with the appropriate antisera and packed as an easy-to-use device that can be self-performed easily. However, it is only useful for the preliminary testing and the confirmation may require advanced laboratory tests. The autocontrol usually present serves as a negative control that does not contain any antibodies in Control well (Ctrl) that validates the test results.²⁵

Solid Phase Red Cell Adherence (SPRCA)

Also known as the Pad system, it is the paper-based blood grouping systems. In such paper-

based analytical device the antisera are immobilized antigens on the absorbant material for simultaneous determination of ABO and Rh blood groups. This kit is made of two different sheets of paper having two different zones. The reverse side has a blood separation zone combined with Whatman paper to separate plasma and serum for reverse grouping. Only monoclonal antisera can be used as DAT samples with such kind of pad systems.¹⁰

Automated Blood Bank Test System

The Blood Center can cater the needs of the patients by focusing on specific blood components during donation with the help of automated blood bank system. Component separation is made easier with the adoption of numerous automated blood bank testing systems. High-quality blood collection that is appropriate for blood component preparation is facilitated by automatic electronic blood collection monitors (BCM) or blood mixers. In order to address patient needs as soon as possible, automated blood donation enables the Blood Center to obtain specific blood components during donation. Red blood cells (RBC), platelets, and plasma are separated using semiautomatic machinery, which has the advantage of removing leucocytes from blood components.²⁶

In an Apheresis, the healthy donor's blood is drawn by a process cell separator machine, which separates the required component and returns the remaining blood to the donor. It is possible to obtain collect separate blood components from the donor, including peripheral blood stem cells, plasma, RBC, platelets, leukocytes and neocytes. Amongst numerous benefits, these devices can offer larger product quantities, due to which a component's entire effective dose is administered all at once. Moreover, there is less exposure to many donors, which lowers the risk of

transfusion-transmitted illnesses and alloimmunization. In addition, the product's quality and purity are superior to those of the manually gathered component.²⁶ In one of the studies conducted by Shin Et al, it was found that ABO/Rh(D) typing a single sample with an automated analyzer had a greater overall cost than testing multiple samples at once, but it was less expensive than testing a single sample manually. The entire price of an unexpected antibody. Compared to the manual method, screening with an automated analyzer was lower.²⁷ A number of factors, including rising transfusion demand, donor safety and selection, donor base changes, product purity, numerous components, product quality, and economics, influences the need for or desirability of RBCs through apheresis or other automated methods.²⁸ An automated blood processor can help further standardize the processing of blood components, which will improve the quality of blood products used in patient treatment.

RECENT METHODS FOR BLOOD GROUPING

Since last few decades, the test tube method blood typing relies on serological assays that detect antigen-antibody reactions. While being effective, these methods have limitations such as reagent dependency, inability to detect weak or rare antigens, and difficulties in patients who have recently received transfusions. Few of the newer techniques are being discussed here

Blood Typing by Plastic Microinjection Moulding

Reaction microchambers, flow splitting microchannels, chaotic micromixers, and detection microfilters are all fully integrated into the biochip. The flow splitting microchannel can split the loaded sample blood into two or four

equal amounts so that two or four blood agglutination tests can be performed simultaneously. To effectively react agglutinogens on red blood cells (RBCs) with agglutinins in serum, a serpentine laminating micromixer was incorporated into the biochip. Chaotic advection and splitting/recombination are two chaotic mixing techniques that are combined in this micromixer. Additionally, relatively large area reaction microchambers were used to maintain the mixing of the sample blood and serum during the reaction phase before filtering.²⁹

Ultrasound Backscattering—Quantitative Measurements of Agglutinates

This novel method is based on ultrasonic backscattering blood group typing. In an acoustic heterogeneous medium, specific alterations in the direction, phase, amplitude, and velocity of sound waves are observed on the red cells without the conversion of mechanical energy into heat. The volume and acoustic properties (elasticity, viscosity, and density) of the red cell surface affect the degree and angle of the dispersed energy. The Doppler effect can be used to record the scattering characteristics of agglutinated red blood cells in comparison to non-agglutinated cells.³⁰

Human Blood Group Typing Based on Digital Photographs of RBC Agglutination Process

A technique based on the *In vitro* agglutination of human red blood cells has been developed for identifying human blood types (groups). The statistical analysis of digital images captured during the agglutination process forms the basis of this technique. Experimental evidence suggests that these images can be used to assess the probability that the erythrocytes in the blood sample would agglutinate in response to the related iso-hemagglutinating sera. The biological specimen is exposed to ultrasonic waves in order

to speed up the erythrocyte agglutination process and increase the method's sensitivity, as previously suggested by the authors. After that, the agglutination reaction's outcomes are assessed visually.³¹

Molecular imprinting: Synthetic materials as substitutes for biological antibodies and receptors.

The versatile technique of molecular imprinting creates useful materials that can identify and, in some cases, react to specific chemical and biological substances of interest. The synthesis of molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) is guided by templates. As a result, it would be more accurate to characterize molecular imprinting as a method founded on "rational design," which permits the resolution of problems pertaining to research and applications. Material scientists may now produce unique synthetic molecules with greatly increased stability using basic chemical building blocks, which can either complement or replace natural receptors.³²

It has been demonstrated by Piletsky, S. S., et al. that natural antibodies in blood group analysis can be replaced with molecularly imprinted nanoparticles specific to blood antigens. Instead of using the current agglutination-based theories, this method is based on magnetically-induced decolorization.³³

Molecular imprinting is one of the most significant contemporary techniques for blood group typing because the synthetic antibodies it produces have similar sensitivity and selectivity to natural antibodies, are easy to make, and can be reused for several tests with sufficient stability. These features make synthetic antibodies superior choices for blood typing and other modern biosensor technologies.³

Blood Group Genotyping

The process of identifying blood group characteristics from specific DNA sequences is known as blood group genotyping. Genotyping is sometimes known as blood group genomic testing or molecular blood grouping. These days, phenotyping methods are less common than genotyping. For instance, information from genomic testing is more precise and dependable if blood group phenotypic information is required but a particular red cell sample is not available; genomic testing is also favored since it might be less costly than serological approaches.³⁴

The genes for the majority of the pertinent blood group systems have been defined as a result of human genome sequencing, and the polymorphisms causing the majority of the clinically significant blood group antigens have been identified. When erythrocytes are unavailable or when serological testing is either impossible or inconclusive due to a lack of antisera, molecular blood group typing is utilized. Additionally, in some circumstances, molecular testing could be more economical. The majority of molecular typing techniques rely on DNA hybridization, DNA sequencing, or PCR using certain primers. In particular, the shift from Sanger-based sequencing to next-generation sequencing (NGS) technologies has created intriguing new opportunities for blood group genotyping.³⁵ Next-generation sequencing, sometimes referred to as massively parallel sequencing, has a high throughput capacity and maps every point of variation from a reference sequence, making it possible to find new SNVs. In general, serological phenotyping and the identification of a complete profile of blood group SNVs serve as a foundation for the supply of compatible blood, improving transfusion safety. SNVs are the most common genetic alteration linked to blood type antigens. SNV mapping, which entails highly multiplexed genotyping, can

be carried out on commercial microarray technologies to predict blood group antigen phenotypes.³⁶

The International Society of Blood Transfusion (ISBT) has identified 48 blood group systems, and single nucleotide variations (SNVs) provide the molecular basis for the expression of all blood type antigens. Numerous DNA assays for blood group antigen prediction were developed using this as their basis. Many clinical troubleshooting problems that hemagglutination was unable to resolve have been resolved by molecular typing of blood type genes in diagnostics. They are essential for determining antigen types for which typing reagents are unavailable.

Patients with warm autoantibodies or those who have recently received a transfusion should be specifically typed; blood group variations should be identified; prenatal testing should be conducted; rare blood types should be sought after; and repositories of antigen-negative red blood cells (RBCs) for transfusion should be made more dependable. Molecular typing of blood group genes is recommended as part of the antibody identification procedure for patients who are transfusion dependent. This is due to the fact that by determining the patient's anticipated phenotype, the lab can ascertain which antigens the patient can and cannot react to in order to generate alloantibodies. Furthermore, molecular typing increases precision and provides more details about the patient's antigenic profile, especially when serological reagents such as unusual blood types and Dombrock (DO) antigens are not available.³⁷³⁸

The power of next-generation sequencing (NGS) of complete genomes or exomes, or by concentrating on specific blood type loci in conjunction with pretransfusion serologic testing, will improve immunohematology in routine transfusion practice.

Real-time quantitative PCR is one medium-

throughput PCR technique for SNP analysis and allele discrimination. Perhaps the most important use of real-time quantitative PCR in immunohaematology is the identification and amplification of the RHD gene from free fetal DNA taken from maternal plasma. The presence of freely circulating fetal DNA in mothers For more than a decade, high-throughput single nucleotide polymorphism-based blood type microarray technology has been available. It was initially developed for the analysis of gene expression in both sick and healthy tissues.

This method uses SNP microarrays with synthetic oligonucleotide probes that contain the desired mutation. A solid phase, such as a glass slide, is where the probes are affixed. The blood group gene around the target mutation is amplified by PCR prior to the products being hybridized with the probe. After rigorous cleaning procedures to ensure specificity, a scanning device analyzes the signals and software evaluates the reactions.

The cost and reimbursement of molecular diagnostics have hindered their widespread usage. However, the cost of molecular detection can be significantly reduced by processing a large number of samples per response using a centralized testing methodology and evaluating many polymorphisms concurrently. Since the introduction of short-read NGS techniques, sequencing costs have also dropped. It is important to keep in mind that molecular testing would only need to be performed once in a lifetime and may be included in the patient transfusion record.³⁹

COMPUTATIONAL APPROACHES FOR BLOOD GROUPING

With the advancement of Bioinformatics, genomics and computational approaches have emerged as powerful tools for predicting blood group phenotypes from genetic information. In-

silico analysis enables researchers and clinicians to interpret DNA sequence data to identify blood group alleles and predict antigen expression and reduced reagent dependency.

A novel, safe, all-inclusive web server algorithm called RBCeq has been developed to effectively evaluate NGS data in the context of transfusion medicine applications. As web server-based blood group genotyping software, it can characterize both known blood group alleles and potential novel alleles that can reduce and silence antigen expression. This solves the computational and storage issues related to processing large raw NGS datasets. It is difficult and time-consuming to analyze NGS data to forecast blood types; RBCeq fills the gaps in this field and will make it easier to apply and translate this technology to enhance patient and blood donor safety.⁴⁰

BloodAGENT is an open-source, flexible tool for determining blood type alleles and evaluating genetic diversity. Under the normal circumstances, bloodAGENT obtains good concordance in blood group allele determination. The findings of this tool demonstrate the resilience of bloodAGENT and its capacity for managing intricate genomic analysis.⁴¹

For thorough and high-throughput RH genotyping from WGS data, Chang et al. designed a computational approach called RHtyper. This method can be applied to patients who already have WGS data and can detect a variety of RH genetic variants found in SCD patients. Currently, the identification of antibodies and the selection of donor units for Rh alloimmunized patients are aided by knowledge of each patient's unique RH genotype. Further investigation is required to ascertain the immunogenicity of particular RH variant alleles in order to improve red cell matching by genotype for SCD patients.⁴²

With its capabilities for data analysis, pattern recognition, and workflow optimization, artificial intelligence (AI) has grown in importance as a tool

in the healthcare industry. AI in transfusion medicine (TM) tackles issues such as patient safety, inventory management, complex immunohematology, and donor recruitment and retention. Clients can improve decision-making, efficiency, and risk reduction by integrating technologies such as machine learning (ML), deep learning, and natural language processing (NLP). The advent of High-throughput computational tools has enabled detection of rare alleles with high accuracy. With the advancements in bioinformatics in blood grouping techniques, which support blood group genotyping, the costs of data processing, storage, and analysis will lower the costs of the sequencing, reducing the overall expenses of the process. However, the bioinformatics algorithms that enable sequencing and blood group characterization techniques need to be optimized, as personal genome sequencing is expected to become more common in the near future. Without improvements to the bioinformatics underlying blood group genotyping, the costs associated with data processing, storage, and analysis will exceed the costs of the sequencing itself, thereby reducing the economic viability of such a strategy. As personal genome sequencing is forecast to become increasingly prevalent in the near future, there is a clear need for the optimization of the bioinformatics algorithms underlying sequencing and blood group characterization approaches.

Blood typing by modern computational techniques helps identify compatible donors and recipients, especially for patients requiring repeated transfusions. Moreover, such analysis can detect rare or novel variants that may not be identifiable through serology. It can be a remarkable investigation in blood group distribution and genetic diversity among diverse populations. Genomic blood typing supports precision medicine by predicting individual blood group profiles.

CONCLUSION

Blood grouping methods have progressed from simple agglutination-based tests to advanced automated and molecular systems. While conventional serological methods remain essential, future developments—especially genotyping, microfluidics, and AI integration—are transforming transfusion medicine toward greater precision, speed, and safety. There are many alternative technologies documented in the literature to identify the agglutination reactions because visual inspection is no longer suitable for collecting exact quantitative information. Modern biosensors and molecular blood type techniques have also been taken into consideration for simple, accurate, and exact analysis, despite the traditional approaches.

It is widely claimed that novel multiplexing methods combined with current blood testing assays will be the future testing algorithms used in blood centres. In transfusion medicine, DNA microarray technology aids in the discovery of novel genes and advances our understanding of infectious diseases. It provides a potentially useful tool for high throughput platelet and red cell antigen genotyping. Future immunohaematology labs may be dominated by this automated method for extended blood group genotyping with multiplex analysis capability.

Though the computational techniques for blood group determination have a few some limitations of specialized infrastructure requirements, Dependency on high-quality sequencing data and Inadequate knowledge of rare variants, Computational bioinformatics approaches have revolutionized blood group determination by enabling genotype-based prediction of blood group antigens. These methods provide a powerful complement to traditional serological testing, particularly for identifying rare variants and understanding antigen structure and function.

Continued advancements in sequencing technologies, databases, and computational algorithms will further improve the reliability and clinical applicability of genomic blood typing in transfusion medicine. Large-scale genomic databases and improved algorithms will enable real-time blood typing and facilitate global rare donor registries.

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